

A STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES ON FACULTIES' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SELF FINANCING COLLEGES

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Abstract:

The article tries to find out the Influence of Knowledge Management Practices on Faculties' job performance in Self Financing colleges. Sample size was 80. Simple random sampling technique was used for primary data collection. Reliability of this tool was 0.92 and 0.88. Multiple regression analysis was used for primary data analysis. It is found that there is an influence of knowledge application, knowledge development, knowledge creation, knowledge storage & representation, knowledge auditing, knowledge acquisition, knowledge filtering, and knowledge strategy on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions. It is also found that there is no influence of like knowledge distribution & exchange and community of practice on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions. It is concluded that majority of the employees are willing to share what they know, the self financing educational institutions are expected to work a lot in changing the attitudes of those who are not willing to share. The self financing educational institution is also expected to use different techniques to extract the knowledge residing with those employees and keep it on the organizational memory.

Key Words: Faculties' Job Performance, Knowledge Management Practices, Self Financing Colleges, Simple Random Sampling Technique & Independent Sample "t" Test

Introduction:

Human Resource is considered to be very crucial in an organization's well being. Today, organizations look upon Human Resources as the most important of all the assets based on the emerging values of humanization. Development is considered to be the soul of the HRM function, which reflects on the organization's effectiveness. Knowledge management in a growing economy like India is the need of the hour. Educational sector in India is the most effective instrument for India's economic development, for which developing Human Resources for this sector has become essential to achieve the national objectives. In spite of the rapid technological reformations, Human Resource remains the backbone of the organizational structure of self financing educational institution in India which undertakes the crucial responsibility of transforming their operational system into a modern one that suits the present requirements.

The word "performance" is used frequently in companies, among human resources personnel and in industrial psychology and management. Regardless of its importance and popularity, it is seldom clearly defined (Neely, Gregory & Platts, 1995). Faculties' job performance is one of the most important dependent variable of interest to educators, business houses, the government and society at large. Researchers and businesses are just now reaching consensus on common definitions and conceptualizations of individual level faculties' job performance. Viswesvaran (2000) pointed out that faculties' job performance is the core constructs of today's work-setting which is making it an important research problem. As such, knowing details of the concept has gained importance. Study of faculties' job performance explains that how employees are working, what kind of training programs should be prescribed for them? Most of the placement decisions depend on the faculties' job performance.

Review of Literature:

Kishokumar (2017) studied about "The Influence of Knowledge Management Factors on Knowledge Management Practices: Special Reference to the Licensed Commercial Banks in Trincomalee District". The principal objective of this study is to examine the influence of knowledge management factors on the management of knowledge. Survey method is the opted research design, and primary data were collected through questionnaires from 150 employees of licensed commercial banks in Trincomalee District. These data were analyzed by adopting multiple regression analysis. The findings of this study indicate that the knowledge management factors and knowledge management practices are of high importance in licensed commercial banks. This study confirms that the knowledge management factors significantly influence knowledge management practices. Hence, the factors, Favorable Transformational Leadership, Organizational Culture and Information Technology factors may lead to better knowledge management practices and contribute to the organization's success and achieve win-win situation. Hence, it can be concluded that the organizations should strengthen their knowledge management factors to improve knowledge management practices.

Danieli Pinto, et al. (2017) studied on "Investigating Knowledge Management within Software Industry: A Systematic Literature Review." This study analyses articles about what instruments are used by researchers within software industry to knowledge management investigate from June 2006 to July 2016 on five electronic databases according to a pre-defined protocol. This is a systematic, literature review method. In this review of literature, eight articles, about instruments towards knowledge management within the software industry were identified. Articles have been systematically reviewed with the assistance of a set of research questions. It was observed that this research subject has not been a common practice within the duration of last ten years. The tools to investigate the knowledge management practices were well structured based on consolidated research on methodological instruments after having some necessary modifications done. The results demonstrated that knowledge management is one among the fundamental processes in the software industry; felt the intensive nature knowledge and its management processes. No studies so far, had analyzed specific proposals of the adopted instruments to investigate knowledge management practices within the software industry.

Latifa Oufkir, Mounia Fredj and Ismail Kassou (2017) studied about the "Performance Measurement for Knowledge Management: Designing a Reference Model." A generic KM performance measurement model fitting any kind of KM projects was proposed by the researchers. This model is an up gradation over the existing KM models found in the literature and enhanced with some up to date theoretical findings. In particular, this research is composed of three interrelated sub-models, namely KM processes, socio-technical influencing KM factors and KM key performance indicators. This study follows the reference modeling design. The various processes are added in view of producing a high quality model.

Hongbo Lyu, Zhiying Zhou and Zuopeng Zhang (2016) had researched on "Measuring Knowledge Management Performance in Organizations: An Integrative Framework of Balanced Scorecard and Fuzzy Evaluation." The research paper investigates the feasibility of the balanced scorecard (BSC) method, in relation to the enterprise knowledge management; along with this the study also proposes a simplified and applicable performance evaluation model based on the BSC approach. In this study Fuzzy comprehensive evaluation (FCE) is used to evaluate the effectiveness and applicability of the proposed model. The result shows that the model is significantly useful for evaluating the performance of KM in enterprises.

Manivannan and Kathiravan (2016) in their study aimed to find out the relationship and impact of knowledge management of bank employees in Chennai city. In this study, Knowledge management includes five dimensions such as knowledge, information technology, organization, top management support and innovation. This is a descriptive study by nature and the data was collected by using questionnaires from the responses of 400 employees from public, private and foreign banks in and around Chennai. Simple random sampling technique was adopted to get the primary data. Research adopted correlation and multiple regression analysis to infer the result of the study. It was found that there is a positive relationship and significant influence towards the knowledge management and the impact over bank employees in Chennai City.

Alexander Serenko and Thunder Bay (2015) studied about "Citation classics published in knowledge management journals. Part I: articles and their characteristics." The study had identified 100 citation classics from seven KM-centric journals based on their citation impact reported by Google Scholar and analyzed their attributes. The KM discipline is at the pre-science stage; because of the influence of normative studies espousing KM practices among institutions. KM is progressing toward normal science and is gaining better momentum toward academic maturity. The scholars from USA and UK have made the most significant impact on the development of the KM school of thought. KM scholars should be more engaged in international collaboration to accumulate desired strength to rise in the level of recognition of KM. Practitioners had played a key role in the development of the KM discipline. There is an opportunity to develop more scientific research approaches based on formative research agenda.

Research Methodology:

Research Design:

To obtain better answer to the research question, a proper research design is to be framed (Cooper & Schindler 2001; Davis & Cosenza 1988). Descriptive research design has been adopted for the present study. Descriptive study is a fact-finding investigation with adequate interpretation. It focuses on particular aspects or dimensions of the problem studied. It is designed to get the descriptive information and provided information and formulation of more sophisticated studies.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To study the influence of knowledge management practices on faculties' job performance in self financing colleges.

Hypothesis of the Study:

- ✓ There is no influence of knowledge management practices on faculties' job performance in self financing colleges.

Sampling Technique:

✓ Simple random sampling technique was adopted for the study. Srivastava (2008) there is only a less effort need to collect the data. Actually no pre plan of executing is there.

Data Collection:

The sample size of the pilot study is 80 in all. The study was conducted in Perambalur district, Tamilnadu. Questionnaire with 5 point scale is used.

Reliability:

For all the items in the questionnaire design the alpha was 0.92 and 0.88. This indicates high reliability of the items in the questionnaire. With these results the consistency, dependability and adoptability are confirmed.

Statistical Tools Used:

Multiple regression analysis was adopted in this study. It is used to know the influence of knowledge management practices on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions.

Analysis and Interpretation:

The Linear multiple regression analysis has been carried out a pilot study sample of 80 and data considering faculties' job performance as a dependent variable and the remaining ten independent factors viz., knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge filtering, knowledge storage & representation, knowledge auditing, knowledge application, knowledge distribution & exchange, knowledge development, community of practice and knowledge strategy. The reaction of the employees and effect of the independent variables on faculties' job performance have been studied by the multiple regression analysis.

Null Hypothesis H₀: There is no influence of knowledge management practices on faculties' job performance in self financing colleges

Alternative Hypothesis H_A: There is an influence of knowledge management practices on faculties' job performance in self financing colleges

Table 1: Result of Multiple Regression Analysis for Influence of Knowledge Management Practices on Faculties' job performance in Self Financing Colleges

R value	R Square	Adj. R Square	SE	F	p
0.9	0.811	0.808	2.17757	308.025	0

Coefficients:

S.No	Knowledge Management Practices	B	SE	Beta	t	p
	Constant	2.572	0.673		3.825	0.001
1	Knowledge Creation	0.251	0.019	0.269	13.191	0.001
2	Knowledge Acquisition	0.162	0.022	0.137	7.282	0.001
3	Knowledge Filtering	0.068	0.019	0.065	3.514	0.001
4	Knowledge Storage & Representation	0.097	0.024	0.079	3.989	0.001
5	Knowledge Auditing	0.281	0.021	0.259	13.2	0.001
6	Knowledge Application	0.153	0.027	0.115	5.663	0
7	Knowledge Distribution & Exchange	0.041	0.026	0.031	1.576	0.115
8	Knowledge Development	0.314	0.027	0.219	11.532	0.001
9	Community of Practice	-0.033	0.021	-0.026	-1.573	0.116
10	Knowledge Strategy	0.286	0.03	0.185	9.682	0.001

Dependent Variable: faculties' job performance

The result of the analysis and computations are given in table 1. The F value obtained for the analysis is 308.025 and the p-value is 0.000 and significant at one percent level. Since the R² is 0.811, the R² shows 81.1% of the efficiency of the model. The knowledge management practices are efficient by 81.1% influencing the faculties' job performance. Hence the assumed regression model may be considered as a good fit.

Considering the significant individual regression coefficients, it is seen that the factors knowledge creation (Beta – 0.269, t – 13.191, P – 0.001), knowledge acquisition (Beta – 0.259, t – 13.2, P – 0.001), knowledge filtering (Beta – 0.219, t – 11.532, P – 0.001), knowledge storage & representation (Beta – 0.185, t – 9.682, P – 0.001), knowledge auditing (Beta – 0.137, t – 7.282, P – 0.001), knowledge application (Beta – 0.115, t – 5.633, P – 0.001), knowledge development (Beta – 0.079, t – 3.989, P – 0.001) and knowledge strategy (Beta – 0.065, t – 3.514, P – 0.001). Hence, the p values are lesser than 0.050 and the null hypotheses are rejected at 1% level of significance. From this multiple regression analysis result, it is concluded that there is an influence of knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge filtering, knowledge storage & representation, knowledge auditing, knowledge application, knowledge development and knowledge strategy on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions. The factors like knowledge distribution & exchange and community of practice obtained p values are greater than 0.050 and not significant. Hence it is concluded that there is no influence of like knowledge distribution & exchange and community of practice faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions.

Findings of the Study:

- ✓ The F value obtained for the analysis is 308.025 and the p-value is 0.000 and significant at one percent level. Since the R^2 is 0.811, the R^2 shows 81.1% of the efficiency of the model. The knowledge management practices are efficient by 81.1% influencing the faculties' job performance. Hence the assumed regression model may be considered as a good fit.
- ✓ There is an influence of knowledge creation, knowledge acquisition, knowledge filtering, knowledge storage & representation, knowledge auditing, knowledge application, knowledge development and knowledge strategy on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions.
- ✓ There is no influence of like knowledge distribution & exchange and community of practice faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions.

Recommendations of the Study:

- ✓ Even if majority of the employees are willing to share what they know, the self financing educational institutions are expected to work a lot in changing the attitudes of those who are not willing to share. The self financing educational institution is also expected to use different techniques to extract the knowledge residing with those employees and keep it on the organizational memory.
- ✓ Majority of the knowledge management practices are not done in a centralized manner. Rather paper based communication is more used to transfer and share knowledge. It is also found out that there is no organizational unit dedicated for knowledge management and also no position for knowledge worker in the organizational structure.

Conclusion of the Study:

It is found that there is an influence of knowledge application, knowledge development, knowledge creation, knowledge storage & representation, knowledge auditing, knowledge acquisition, knowledge filtering, and knowledge strategy on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions. It is also found that there is no influence of like knowledge distribution & exchange and community of practice on faculties' job performance in self financing educational institutions. It is concluded that majority of the employees are willing to share what they know, the self financing educational institutions are expected to work a lot in changing the attitudes of those who are not willing to share. The self financing educational institution is also expected to use different techniques to extract the knowledge residing with those employees and keep it on the organizational memory.

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